

GAIA Green Awareness in Action: PRE- AND POST-INTERVENTION QUESTIONNAIRES

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1. Survey of students' awareness of energy-related issues (pre-intervention)

SCHOOL INFORMATION

- School:

- Age: label=
 - Primary school (6-12 year-old)
 - Lower secondary school (12-15 year-old)
 - Upper secondary school (15-18 year-old)

- Sex: label=
 - Boy
 - Girl

ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENERGY SAVING

1) What is your attitude towards saving energy? (Choose one)

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- Much
- Very much

2) How aware are you of the impact of energy use on the environment? (Choose one)

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- Much
- Very much

3) How much energy do you consume at home? (Choose one)

- Not at all
- A little
- Some
- Much
- Very much

4) Where do you apply your knowledge in practice? (Choose one)

- I try to save energy every day at home as well as at school
- I save energy only at home
- I save energy only at school
- I am not interested in saving energy

5) How sensitized are you to energy waste? (Choose one)

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- Much
- Very much

6) Are you motivated to save energy? (Choose one)

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- Much
- Very much

7) Which of the following devices are found in your home? (Check all that apply)

- Computer
- Laptop
- DVD Player
- Vacuum cleaner
- TV
- Stereo
- Mobile phone
- Wireless phone
- Washing machine
- Dish washer
- Water heater
- Iron
- Hair drier
- Hair straightener
- Air heater
- Microwave oven
- Oven
- Refrigerator and freezer
- Mixer
- Refrigerator
- Air condition

8) From the above list, which four devices are in your opinion responsible for the biggest energy consumption in your home?

9) How often do you leave the lights turned on when there is no one in the room? (Choose one)

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Most of the times
- Always

10) How often do you leave a device charging even if its battery has already been fully charged? (Choose one)

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Most of the times
- Always

11) How often do you leave your computer turned on while it is not in use? (Choose one)

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Most of the times
- Always

12) How often do you leave your devices (e.g., DVD player, computer screen, speakers) in stand-by? (Choose one)

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes

- Most of the times
- Always

13) Have you had the opportunity to decrease energy consumption at your home?

- Yes
- No

14) If you controlled energy consumption at home, do you believe this would help you to become more sensitized to the importance of saving energy?

- Yes
- No

15) Do you know ways to save energy? (Choose one)

- I know many ways to save energy
- I know 3-4 ways to save energy
- I know some basic ways to save energy
- I don't know any way to save energy

16) Do you use energy saving techniques at home?

- Yes
- No

17) If so, choose which of the following you use: (Check all that apply)

- I use energy-saving lamps
- I turn off the lights and check that the devices are turned off before I leave the house
- I use low-energy-consumption devices
- I try to change my daily habits to save energy
- Other:

2. Survey of students' awareness of energy-related issues (post-intervention)

Please answer the following questions carefully. Your answers are anonymous and will not affect anyone's opinion about you. It is very important to help us understand how young people like you think.

Tell us about you:

I am...

- a girl
- a boy
- I don't want to say.

My age is...

- up to 11-12 years
- From 12-13 to 14-15 years
- From 15-16 to 17-18+ years

The name of my school:

Let's start!

Think of energy consumption every day: for lighting, heating, traveling, working, reading, having fun... And think about what you learned and did at your school about energy consumption and energy saving.

I know about and I understand...

Q1. ...the consequences of wasting energy for the environment:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Well
- Very well

Q2. ...in what ways we consume energy at school and in everyday life:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Well
- Very well

Think fast:

Q3. How many ways of saving energy come to your mind immediately?

- None
- One
- A few (e.g. 1-2)
- Some (e.g. 3-4)
- Many

After what we have done at school about saving energy...

Q4. ... I've tried to change some of my everyday habits to save energy:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Much
- Very much

Q5. ...I will advise or even tell someone off, if I see that they waste energy:

- Never, I don't think I should.
- Maybe, but generally I avoid this.
- Yes, but only if the waste of energy seems to be big.
- Yes, of course, this is very important!

Q6. ...I try to stay informed about energy and environmental problems:

- Never, this topic is boring.
- Generally, I try, but it's a bit boring.
- Quite often, especially if I need that for school.
- Often, I am interested in this topic.
- Very often, that's extremely important!

Think fast:

Q7. What did you do yesterday and today to save energy?

- Almost nothing.
- I thought about that a couple of times.
- I thought about that many times.
- I tried to save energy through my choices and practice.
- I did really a lot to save energy; I paid attention to this matter all the time.

With what we have done recently at my school...

Q8. ...we have managed to save energy in the school:

- No, I don't think we tried.
- No, we tried but it was difficult.
- Yes, we have probably saved energy, but I don't know how much.
- Yes, we have saved energy and I know some details about this.

From the things we did at school about saving energy:

Q9. ...I liked the game (“GAIA Challenge”):

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Much
- Very much
- I don't think I played the game.

Q10. ...I liked to observe and use the data and measurements:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Much
- Very much
- I don't think I worked with data and measurements.

Q11. ...I liked the lab activity with the circuits etc.:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so

- Much
- Very much
- I don't think I took part in such an activity.

I learned a lot of interesting things about energy...

Q12. ... by playing the digital game (“GAIA Challenge”):

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Much
- Very much
- I don't think I played the game.

Q13. ...I learned a lot by observing and using the data and measurements:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Much
- Very much
- I don't think I worked with data and measurements.

Q14. ...I learned a lot in the lab activity with the circuits etc.:

- Not at all
- A little
- So and so
- Much
- Very much
- I don't think I took part in such an activity.

And a last thing: please think and tell us...

...about a case when you managed to do something important against wasting energy at your school or at home (in a few words):

...what makes it difficult for you to pay more attention to energy consumption in everyday life (in a few words):

...what you would like to do at school next year to learn more about saving energy (in a few words):

Have you answered all questions? Then, "SUBMIT"!

Remember: Your careful attention and the truth in your answers will be a real help in the efforts to use energy smartly and save our planet from the dangers of climate change! Thank you very much for your help!